

School Principals' Role in Achieving Distance-Learning Success during COVID-19 Pandemic: Developmental Proposals

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 02, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Distance Learning, COVID-19, School Principals</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5550346</p>	<p><i>The aim of the current study is to examine the role of school principals in achieving distance-learning success during COVID-19 pandemic, and to propose developmental suggestions attributing to its success. The sample of the study consisted of (332) male and female teachers selected randomly from both public and private schools. To achieve the purposes of the study, questionnaire and personal interviews were used. From teachers' perceptions, the results indicated that school principals' role in achieving distance-learning success during COVID-19 pandemic was moderate. The study found that there are statistically significant differences in school principals' role in achieving distance-learning success from teachers' perceptions, due to gender (in favor of females); due to school type (in favor of private schools); and due to experience (in favor of less than 10 years). Whereas, there were no statistically significant differences due to the educational level. In light of the findings, a set of recommendations were suggested.</i></p>

Introduction

Nowadays, the whole world is witnessing a pandemic threatening the life of all humanity. Due to the lack of a vaccine to put an end for this pandemic and enables the medical bodies to control it, the outbreak of Coronavirus has caused panic, anxiety and despair about future. Furthermore, it has forced societies to take many changes in all aspects of life by enforcing individuals to coexist with the crisis through taking resolute actions, such as social distancing and partial or sometimes complete lockdowns.

Educational administration is an integral part of any educational institution, through which the desired educational objectives, that are consistent with the sound education of the local community members, are attained. School administration refers to all organized efforts exerted by the educational staff (principals and teachers) within the framework of the school or the organizational institution. It is a set of employment processes carried out by others through the organization, arrangement, coordination and supervision with the aim of implementing and achieving school tasks affecting individuals' behavior and education (Musa & Martha, 2020).

Bostanci, Kalsen, Tosun and Dogan, (2020) define school administration as a set of operational processes and coordinated efforts exerted through the intellectual, psychological and material cooperation of teachers and principals, an encouraging workers to make efforts and work actively, whether individually or collectively, as a way of solving problems, and achieving schools' previously planned educational, social and pedagogical objectives of highest efficiency and minimum of time and effort within an appropriate environment inside or outside schools and in accordance with country policies that are consistent with society's goals. In view of the foregoing, the researcher defines school administration as the strategies devised by the principal and applied by teachers, throughout setting the foundations, plans and policies through which the educational process and personnel's performance are controlled, and through which the various problems and conditions facing the school can be addressed in a systematic manner ensuring the achievement of educational objectives, as well as improvement educational outcomes quality.

According to Dos and Savas (2015), the characteristics of effective school administration are embodied in its ability to exercise leadership at all levels with respect to the quality of education and educational objectives; to adopt more than one strategy; to provide clear and sound organizational structures; to involve all personnel within the educational process in a way promoting their career practices, to develop its personnel using a methodology fulfilling both collective and individual needs; to promote positive behavior; to achieve creativity in teaching methods; and to engage parents in the educational process.

Furthermore, a school administration's effectiveness and success are clearly evidenced by the attitudes enabling it to practice the appropriate leadership style, in addition to the personal characteristics of the educational leader, since it is the effective leadership style through which educational leaders can achieve the targeted objectives (Badarna&Heib, 2016).

Unfortunately, Corona pandemic has negatively affected the education process. It forced students to stop their traditional styles of education (face to face), especially students in the primary stage, which is one of the most sensitive stages affecting students' skills, knowledge and attitudes towards learning. Additionally, both school principals and personnel have to handle this unexpected situation through urging teachers to adopt distance-learning (Almaiah, Al-Khasawneh & Althunibat, 2020).

In this sense, the competent authorities sought to develop and manage the educational system more effectively through activating distance learning system in order to ensure education maintenance; avoid interruption; enhance educational institutions' effectiveness in addressing all crises and disasters, contribute to identifying the necessary practices to successfully confront the pandemic; maintaining the quality of education; and ensuring that teachers and students are positively oriented to modern teaching methods (Cerezo, Bogarín, Esteban & Romero, 2020).

In order for teachers to be aware of their educational and social responsibility, and to urge them move from memorization to organizing, instructing, and evaluating, the Jordanian Ministry of Education launched training programs for teachers, (Almamlaka Website, 2020).

Distance-learning can be identified as a modern educational method depends on student's effort and self-reliance to obtain a school or university degree, and uses technology (e.g. internet, computers, smartphones ... etc.) to achieve the educational objectives. It does not need walls, desks or even classrooms requiring students to be face to face with their teacher as in the traditional methods of teaching (Radha, Mahalakshmi, Sathis Kumar & Saravanakumar, 2020).

Rajabion and his colleague (2019) illustrate that distance-learning is a type of teaching relying on self-learning through the use of modern technologies to communicate knowledge and to achieve both direct and indirect interaction with their teachers regardless the time or the place they are in. Hasan and Bao (2020) claim that distance learning is the widespread use of technology to achieve flexibility in time, and design educational curricula ensuring students' self-learning and the social acceptance of this modern method. Distance-learning is achieved through the use of various means and multiple, disparate sources to communicate and transfer science and knowledge to students directly. Therefore, it helps students to develop and improve their skills in using the Internet, computers and other multi-technological media.

The importance of distance-learning stems from its ability to provide a mechanism ensuring the maintenance of the educational process via multiple communication media relying on modern technologies to work. Compared to traditional education, it helps students to be free from time and place constraints; modern technology means can be used to better motivate and reinforce students to overcome sudden obstacles, circumstances and crises without a need to interrupt their educational process (Wargadinata, Maimunah, Dewi & Rofiq, 2020).

Upon the sudden and wide spread of the Coronavirus, the world was not fully prepared to confront such a pandemic. This caused most countries to take swift and decisive actions to preliminarily coexist with the pandemic and then be able to develop a vaccine puts an end for this pandemic. Thus, most countries headed toward applying distance-learning as precautionary measure helping people have normal life, but, in different and modern ways (Dhawan, 2020). Upon the application Distance-Learning, teachers and students faced many obstacles, such as the difficulty to afford the technological infrastructure of devices and Internet access required for achieving communication between the teacher and students, in addition to the lack of community awareness and its individuals' negative perceptions towards the application of distance-learning, causing them to reluctance and refuse this educational system (Almanthari, Maulina & Bruce, 2020). Beside countries ability to provide material, technical and technological capabilities, distance-learning requires training competence human forces to cover the huge numbers of students, facilitate the educational process, maintaining educational outcomes quality and improving students' academic achievement (Kapasias et al., 2020).

Several studies addressed the needed skills for the success of distance learning. For example, Seneca (2008) conducted a study in the United States aimed to identify the required leadership skills for principals and educators during the application of distance-learning in the state of Louisiana from their point of view. To achieve the purpose of the study, the quantitative and qualitative design was used. The study sample consisted of (101) principals. The results of the study indicated that there is a need for school principals to understand how to appropriately apply distance-learning and how to use technology more effectively. It also indicated their need to have a tendency to keep pace with the continuous learning process, and then by able to assess their skills.

Blau and Presser (2013) conducted a study sought to identify principals' administrative skills required for directing distance-learning through the educational platform "Mashov" at the end of 2010/2011 academic year. To achieve the study objectives, semi-structured interviews were used. The study consisted of (10) samples: (8) secondary school principals, a Ministry of Education supervisor, and a director of the school principals' training program. The results of the study indicated that Mashov platform provided an extensive support for school principals in managing their institutions, delegating responsibilities and enhancing their leadership skills, which in turn increased the educational effectiveness of their schools. The study also indicated that distance-learning management is a responsibility of school principals.

Machado and Chung (2015) conducted a study in the United States aimed to assess current trends related to introducing technology in schools from principals' perspectives, as well as principals' focus on using technology in education. To achieve its purposes, the study used a questionnaire. The sample of the study consisted of (200) school principals selected from (4) schools in California. The results of the study revealed that the majority of participated principals in this study give a great importance to the use of technology in education, and that they realize that both teacher readiness and professional development may represent the main obstacles preventing the application of distance learning. The result also indicated that teachers' training on the application of distance-learning represents an ideal solution to achieve the success of using technology in education.

Raman, Thannimalai and Ismail (2019) aimed in their study to examine the effect of technological leadership on school principals and its relationship with teachers' ability to apply distance-learning in education. The sample of the study consisted of (47) principals and (375) teachers selected randomly from the national secondary schools of Keda, Malaysia. To achieve the purpose of the study, a questionnaire was used. The results of the study showed no statistically significant correlation between the principals' technological leadership and teachers' application of distance-learning in education.

Elfrianto, Dahniyal and Tanjung (2020), conducted in Indonesia, aimed to identify school principals' efficiency – being the leaders within the educational environment - in following up teachers' commitment to applying distance-learning rules during Corona pandemic. To achieve the purpose of the study, the qualitative methodology based on content analysis of previous literature was used. The findings of the study revealed that the level of principals' leadership skills is considered essential, not only during Corona pandemic, but also in typical situations. The finding also indicated that school principals should provide an opportunity for teachers to develop their technological competencies.

From the above, it follows that researchers were interested in examining the role of school principals in activating distance-learning system, as we saw that (Seneca, 2008) aimed to identify the required leadership skills for principals and educators during the application of distance-learning, and that (Blau & Presser study, 2013) sought to identify principals' administrative skills required for directing distance-learning.

As for its methodology, the current study used the quantitative methodology and this design is different from the study of Elfrianto, Dahniyal and Tanjung, (2020) that uses the qualitative methodology. The current study is different from previous ones in being, according to the researcher's limited knowledge, one of the first studies addressing role of the school principals in achieving the successes of distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic, and in its attempt to provide a set of proposals contributing to its development from the perspectives of private secondary school principals in Irbid governorate. It also capitalized on previous literature in enriching its theoretical framework, developing the instruments of the study, selecting the appropriate statistical procedures, discussing the findings and proposing recommendations.

The Problem of the Study

No doubt that Corona pandemic has affected various educational aspects, including teaching and learning process, increasing therefore the importance of and need for distance-learning as a solution. Despite all the obstacles that faced the implementation of distance-learning, it has become an urgent necessity as a result of various health authorities' regulations related to social distancing, which means that students cannot be taught in the usual ways.

Being one of education's most important pillars, school administration had to be up to the responsibility in order to help in overcoming the pandemic's consequences. Therefore, school administration's effectiveness and ability to assume its responsibility were not among the research issues addressed by the previous literature, due to the fact that most of those studies focuses on the effectiveness of school administration in natural conditions, without taking into consideration the emergency situations that may imposed on school administrations to give up the traditional forms of education, and without providing effective solutions helps both teachers and learners in achieving their educational objectives. In addition to that, the current study attempts to bridge the theoretical and practical gap of the previous literature, related to the effectiveness of educational administration in applying distance-learning during Corona pandemic being one of the issues that has not received much attention by the educational literature. Thus, the problem of the study stems from its attempt to answer the following questions:

- What is the level of school administration role in achieving the success of distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic from teachers' perspectives?
- What are the problems facing distance-learning application during COVID-19 pandemic in Jordanian schools from principals' perspectives?
- What are the potential proposals for developing distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic in Jordanian schools from principals' perspectives?

The Purpose of the study

The purposes of the study are as follows:

- Identifying the level of school administration role in achieving the success of distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic from teachers' perspectives.
- Determining the differences school administration's role in achieving the success of distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic from teachers' perspectives in light of some variables (Experience, Educational Level, Gender, Educational Sector).
- Illustrating the problems facing the application of distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic in Jordanian schools from principals' perspectives, as well as providing asset of proposals for its development.

The Significance of the Study

The significance of the current study stems from the fact that it addresses one of the most important themes at present (the role of the school administration in achieving the success of distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic), and provide a set of proposals for the development of distance-learning. Furthermore, it attempts to drive the attention of the educators and those in charge of the educational process towards developing school administration practices, so that they can effectively apply distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic, things that may affect teachers' ability to fulfill their work duties and students' achievement, in addition to develop a set of procedures can be adopt by schools to appropriately develop their application of distance-learning.

Terms Definitions

Effectiveness: It is a standard an individual's or a group's level of fulfilling their duties adequately.

School Administration: It is a set of operational processes and coordinated efforts exerted through the intellectual, psychological and material cooperation of teachers and principals, an encouraging workers to make efforts and work actively, whether individually or collectively, as a way of solving problems, and achieving schools' previously planned educational, social and pedagogical objectives of highest efficiency and minimum of time and effort within an appropriate environment inside or outside schools and in accordance with country policies that are consistent with society's goals (Bostanci, Kalsen, Tosun&Dogan, 2020).

Distance learning: A modern educational method depends on student's effort and self-reliance to obtain a school or university degree, and uses technology (e.g. internet, computers, smartphones ... etc.) to achieve the educational objectives. It does not need walls, desks or even classrooms requiring students to be face to face with their teacher as in the traditional methods of teaching (Radha, Mahalakshmi, Sathis Kumar & Saravanakumar, 2020).

Third Level Headings

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Table 1. Centre the Caption above the Table

Variables		N	Mean
Group	1.	47	30.3
	2.	60	38.7
	3.	48	31.0
Age	18-21	150	96.8
	other	5	3.2
Gender	F	117	75.5
	M	38	24.5
Total		155	100

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Methods and Procedures

The study adopts a mixed methods design as both quantitative descriptive analytical design (questionnaire) and open-ended personal interview (qualitative) were employed for data collection.

Population and Sample of the Study

The study population consisted of all public and private schools teachers at Irbid city who works in the first semester for the educational year 2020/2021. A random sample consisted of (332) school teachers were selected in order to achieve the study objectives. Additionally, a purposefully sample consisted of (20) school principals were selected for the interviews that were conducted through phone. Table (1) shows the distribution of the study (School teachers) according to the study variables.

Table 1. Frequencies and Percentages According to the Study Variables

Variable	Category	Frequency	%
Gender	Male	135	40.7%
	Female	197	59.3%
Educational Level	BA	202	60.8%
	Higher Education	130	39.2%
Type of School	Governorate	194	58.4%
	Private	138	41.6%
Experience	Less than 10 Years	123	37.0%
	10-15 Years	114	34.3%
	More than 15 Years	95	28.6%
Sum		332	100%

Study Instrument

To achieve the study objectives the researcher developed the study instrument by reviewing a set of previous studies.

The Instrument Validity

To check content validity of the instrument, a jury of (10) specialized members of faculty members in educational administration and fundamentals were asked to give their remarks about the items suitability, the authenticity of its phrasing, clarity, and their appropriateness to the domain they belong to. (80%) of the proposed amendments by the juries were taken into consideration. To obtain construct validity, correlation coefficients between the items and the total score through a pilot sample consisted of (30) teachers. Correlation coefficient of each item was calculated, as the correlation value indicates validity significance for each item since it indicates the correlation value between the item and the total score from one hand and between each domain and the total score on the other hand. The correlation coefficient of the items and the total score ranged between (0.39-0.76), and with the domain (0.39-0.85) as shown in the following table.

Table 2. Correlation Coefficients between the Items, the Total Score and the Domain to which they belong

Item	correlation coefficients to the domain	correlation coefficients to the instrument	Item	correlation coefficients to the domain	correlation coefficients to the instrument	Item	correlation coefficients to the domain	correlation coefficients to the instrument
1	0.52(**)	0.54(**)	12	0.74(**)	0.69(**)	23	0.75(**)	0.72(**)
2	0.63(**)	0.40(*)	13	0.58(**)	0.55(**)	24	0.82(**)	0.73(**)

3	0.63(**)	0.39(*)	14	0.64(**)	0.61(**)	25	0.69(**)	0.67(**)
4	0.39(*)	0.39(*)	15	0.71(**)	0.66(**)	26	0.57(**)	0.55(**)
5	0.69(**)	0.39(*)	16	0.63(**)	0.43(**)	27	0.59(**)	0.53(**)
6	0.71(**)	0.59(**)	17	0.80(**)	0.63(**)	28	0.79(**)	0.69(**)
7	0.71(**)	0.68(**)	18	0.73(**)	0.61(**)	29	0.85(**)	0.76(**)
8	0.53(**)	0.57(**)	19	0.63(**)	0.45(**)	30	0.69(**)	0.56(**)
9	0.85(**)	0.65(**)	20	0.59(**)	0.41(**)	31	0.58(**)	0.60(**)
10	0.79(**)	0.71(**)	21	0.57(**)	0.40(**)	32	0.49(**)	0.45(**)
11	0.60(**)	0.46(*)	22	0.59(**)	0.55(**)	33	0.66(**)	0.59(**)

* Significant at (0.05)

** Significant at (0.01)

It can be noted that all the correlation coefficients were expected and significant, and for that none of the scale items have been deleted.

Reliability

To verify the instrument reliability, test-retest method was used by administrating the instrument and re-administrating it after two weeks on a sample consisting of (30) teachers selected from the same population and out of the original sample. Pearson's correlation factor was calculated between their responses in both times. Then, Pearson Correlation was calculated between their scores on the scale. Furthermore, Cronbach Alpha Coefficient for internal consistency reliabilities was calculated. Table (3) shows internal consistency reliabilities for the individual domains and the total instrument. It can be noted that these values are appropriate to achieve the objectives of the study.

Table 3. Cronbach Alpha Internal Consistency Reliabilities for Individual Domains and Total Instrument

Domain	Test-Retest Reliability	Internal Consistency Coefficient
Distance learning administration requirements related to principals	0.90	0.84
Distance learning administration requirements related to teachers	0.92	0.86
Distance learning administration requirements related to curricula	0.90	0.82
Distance learning administration requirements related to the organizational and Technical aspects	0.91	0.80
Total score	0.91	0.89

Table (3) shows that internal consistency coefficient for the implementation of distance learning ranged between (0.84-0.89).

Study Results and Discussion

Results of the First Question: "What is the level of school administration role in achieving the success of distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic from teachers' perspectives?"

To answer this question, means and standard deviations for the level of school administration role in achieving the success of distance learning during COVID-19 pandemic from teachers' perspective, as seen in the following table.

Table 4. Means and Standard deviations for the Level of School Administration Role in Achieving the Success of Distance Learning from Teachers Perspective in A Descending Order

Rank	Number	Domain	Means	Std. Devi	Level
1	2	Distance learning administration requirements related to teachers	3.00	0.713	Moderate
2	1	Distance learning administration requirements related to principals	2.79	1.037	Moderate
3	4	Distance learning administration requirements related to the	2.70	0.940	Moderate

		organizational and Technical aspects			
4	3	Distance learning administration requirements related to curricula	2.59	0.893	Moderate
Total score			2.78	0.841	Moderate

Table (4) shows that the means ranged between (2.59-3.00) as distance learning administration requirements related to teachers ranked first ($M = 3.00$), while distance learning administration requirements related to curricula ranked last ($M = 2.59$), the mean of the total score is (2.78) with a moderate level. Additionally, means and standard deviations for the study sample responses on the items of the instrument domains were calculated as follow.

First Domain: Distance learning administration requirements related to principals

Table 5. Means and Standard deviations for Distance Learning Administration Requirements Related to Principals in a Descending Order

Rank	Number	Item	Means	Std. Devi.	Level
1	2	School principal uses e-mail to contact with teachers and to follow up the students through it.	3.17	1.292	Moderate
2	5	School principal provide educational courses concerning the mechanism of using distance learning system for teachers during COVID-19 pandemic.	2.91	1.272	Moderate
3	6	School principal tests and define a social media that provide direct communication between the principal, teacher and the students.	2.89	1.254	Moderate
4	1	School principal supervise and organize the distance learning process during COVID-19 pandemic.	2.76	1.354	Moderate
5	3	School principal uses mailing groups, discussion groups and webinars with teachers and students.	2.70	1.303	Moderate
6	4	School principal uses software in preparing the educational plan with teachers.	2.61	1.279	Moderate
7	7	School principal assess the functioning of distance learning process and provides feedback to improve and develop students' outcomes.	2.53	1.387	Moderate
Distance learning administration requirements related to principals			2.79	1.037	Moderate

Table (5) shows that the means ranged between (2.53-3.17) as item (2) stating "School principal uses e-mail to contact with teachers and to follow up the students through it" ranked first ($M = 3.17$), while item (7) stating "School principal assess the functioning of distance learning process and provides feedback to improve and develop students' outcomes" ranked last ($M = 2.53$). Mean of the total score for distance learning administration requirements related to principals is (2.79) with a moderate level.

Second Domain: Distance learning administration requirements related to teachers

Table 6. Means and Standard deviations for Distance Learning Administration Requirements Related to Teachers in a Descending Order

Rank	Number	Item	Means	Std. Devi.	Level
1	14	Teacher uses various multimedia (sound, pictures, videos) in teaching the electronic content for students.	3.36	1.086	Moderate
2	12	Teacher uses Chat applications to facilitate communication with the students.	3.34	1.130	Moderate
3	13	Teacher defines the goals of e-curricula based on criteria agreed with the principal.	3.26	1.023	Moderate
4	8	Teacher uses the Internet to prepare the study plan to complete the e-learning	3.15	1.264	Moderate

5	11	process in an appropriate way. Teacher uses e-storage media related to curriculum in order to save and retrieve it in any time.	2.98	1.327	Moderate
6	15	Teacher evaluates students and follows them in distance learning.	2.70	1.225	Moderate
7	9	Teacher uses multimedia to present the curricula to be taught via distance learning.	2.66	1.261	Moderate
8	10	Teacher uses the Internet to search for information related to curricula to be taught.	2.54	1.069	Moderate
Distance learning administration requirements related to teachers			3.00	0.713	Moderate

Table (6) shows that the means ranged between (2.54-3.36) as item (14) stating "Teacher uses various multimedia (sound, pictures, videos) in teaching the electronic content for students" ranked first ($M = 3.36$), while item (10) stating "Teacher uses the Internet to search for information related to curricula to be taught" ranked last ($M = 2.54$). Mean of the total score for distance learning administration requirements related to teachers is (2.79) with a moderate level.

Third Domain: Distance learning administration requirements related to curricula

Table 7. Means and Standard deviations for Distance Learning Administration Requirements Related to Curricula in a Descending Order

Rank	Number	Item	Means	Std. Devi.	Level
1	22	Adding drawings and shapes related to the curricula attract students' attention.	2.92	1.262	Moderate
2	21	Including different questions and activities to the curricula.	2.75	1.137	Moderate
3	17	The online curriculum is continuously available to students.	2.62	1.229	Moderate
4	20	Using well-developed programs to explain the curriculum so they can be easily modified in case any changes occurred to the curriculum.	2.62	1.137	Moderate
5	16	Organizing the curriculum and creating step-by-step presentation plan commensurate with different levels of students.	2.60	1.153	Moderate
6	18	E-curriculum includes tools for positive interaction between teacher and students.	2.54	1.092	Moderate
7	19	Diversity in the presentation of curriculum content to suit students' mental abilities.	2.06	1.166	Moderate
Distance learning administration requirements related to curricula			2.59	0.893	Moderate

Table (7) shows that the means ranged between (2.06-2.92) as item (22) stating "Adding drawings and shapes related to the curricula attract students' attention" ranked first ($M = 2.92$), while item (19) stating "Diversity in the presentation of curriculum content to suit students' mental abilities" ranked last ($M = 2.06$). Mean of the total score for distance learning administration requirements related to curricula is (2.59) with a moderate level.

Fourth Domain: Distance learning administration requirements related to organizational and technical aspects

Table 8. Means and Standard deviations for Distance Learning Administration Requirements Related to Organizational and Technical Aspects in a Descending Order

Rank	Number	Item	Means	Std. Devi.	Level
1	29	Allocating part of the school budget to support distance learning.	3.02	1.222	Moderate
2	28	Defining organized criteria to assess the teaching process for the teacher, students' understanding and achievement level.	2.99	1.332	Moderate
3	27	Students' interaction in distance learning has been affected by the special and difficult living conditions.	2.91	1.301	Moderate

4	30	Preparing a technical team specializing in software necessary for the distance learning process.	2.76	1.184	Moderate
5	26	Following an effective strategy to deal with the students' large number in distance learning.	2.70	1.238	Moderate
6	25	Providing appropriate internet speed and uninterrupted during the learning process from students and teachers sides.	2.64	1.232	Moderate
7	23	Providing a distance learning system appropriate with the theoretical and practical curriculum content.	2.58	1.269	Moderate
8	24	Teachers need to possess sufficient experience and skills appropriate to use the computer and the internet.	2.18	1.111	Moderate
Distance learning administration requirements related to organizational and technical aspects			2.70	0.940	Moderate

Table (8) shows that the means ranged between (2.18-3.02) as item (29) stating "Allocating part of the school budget to support distance learning" ranked first ($M = 3.02$), while item (24) stating "Teachers need to possess sufficient experience and skills appropriate to use the computer and the internet" ranked last ($M = 2.18$). Mean of the total score for distance learning administration requirements related to administration and technical aspects is (2.70) with a moderate level.

Results of the Second Question: "What are the problems facing distance-learning application during COVID-19 pandemic in Jordanian schools from principals' perspectives?"

The study revealed that poor infrastructure in schools was one of the most problems that hinder the application of distance learning from principals' point of view. Considering the infrastructure is the base of distance learning then there is a need to provide devices and teachers' adequate training to provide the appropriate distance learning for the students to meet the learning requirements under COVID-19 pandemic.

For example, one of the principals mentioned that: *"The school lack the adequate infrastructure to provide distance learning, especially in light of the conditions Jordan is facing due to COVID-19 pandemic. Whereas COVID-19 pandemic lead to stop face-to-face education and resort to distance learning as an alternative solution in order to provide the adequate learning for students, schools are still unable to provide this service optimally due to the lack of resources in schools (Computers, internet connection... etc.) which are necessary to provide distance learning"*

UN report (2020) confirms that developing countries including Jordan facing difficulties due to the poor infrastructure during COVID-19 pandemic to shift for distance learning. Given that infrastructure is one of the basic elements in the success of this educational experience; school principals express their dissatisfaction with the available infrastructure to increase school administration effectiveness in achieving the success of distance learning.

Confirming this, one of the principals pointed that the Jordanian high schools still unable to provide high-quality distance learning due to the poor infrastructure, he says:

"One of the most important problems that my school faces is the unavailability of the needed devices and the poor internet connection, and this has a negative impact on the education output. Teachers are unable to interact with students sufficiently and provide the learning content in an appropriate method".

The principal above indicates that the unavailability of computers and the poor access to the internet are one of the main problems faces the school he runs and this goes for most Jordanian schools which got surprised by the shift to distance learning as a final solution to deliver the appropriate learning for students.

The results also showed that one of the important obstacles to the distance learning success is the low level of technological competencies among school teachers. Technological competencies in distance learning are considered an importance issue faces school principals and this problem has been exacerbated by school teachers' inability to deal with educational technologies, as they unable to provide the learning content to students appropriately. Furthermore, teachers' inability to employ effective assessment strategies clearly lead to the low quality of the learning content provided. One of the principals mentioned that:

"Teachers expressed their inability to use the computer sufficiently to deliver the learning content as hoped; they are also still unable to deal with the teaching technologies and to use the platforms which need lots of training and practice to be adequately mastered and used effectively".

Al-Adwan (2019) confirmed in her study that teachers still do not have the needed technological competencies to apply distance learning perfectly, especially that it has become the strategic option in delivering the e-learning content during COVID-19 pandemic and this made it the base in the current educational process. Since distance learning has become the alternative to the face-to-face learning in the Jordanian schools this study recommended to develop teachers' preparation programs so they can become able to provide the learning content using the various technological means.

One of the principals stated: *"Teachers cannot use distance learning technologies perfectly due to the lacking of the needed competencies to apply distance learning and since COVID-19 pandemic was unexpected thing, the sudden transformation to distance learning forced the teachers to use high-level technological competencies, something that teachers lack especially those of the higher age group something that teachers lack especially those in the higher age group"*.

The nature of the curriculum is also one of the main challenges in the success of distance learning. Principals mentioned that the educational curriculum is not flexible enough to deliver it via distance learning. The principals also mentioned that teachers show difficulty in transforming the learning content electronically for the students although most of the educational curricula provided in a partially computerized version in schools. They also mentioned that scientific subjects such as mathematics and science got were the most affected by the transition to distance learning.

In this regard, a principal mentioned that: *"Jordanian curriculum are not fully computerized to be delivered via distance learning which has become a clear reality during COVID-19 pandemic, for this reason there is a need to fully computerize the school curriculum so the teachers become able to deliver it to students using distance assessment strategies to ensure that educational objectives are achieved.*

El-Hasanat (2012) pointed that school curriculum need to be developed to adapt to the role of educational technology in teaching it. This was confirmed by the results of the interviews where principals indicated that the nature of the curriculum still lack the adequate flexibility to be fully computerized and become able to deliver the suitable educational content to the students.

Results of the Third Question: "What are the potential proposals for developing distance-learning during COVID-19 pandemic in Jordanian schools from principals' perspectives?"

The results of the study revealed that developing schools infrastructure was one of the most important issues that must be considered in order to achieve the success of distance learning. Some studies such as UN (2020) report have pointed to the status of the schools infrastructure in the developing countries and that there is a need to work on developing it so it can response effectively to the needs of distance learning. Principals who participated in the current study confirmed this fact where one of them mentioned:

"Working on developing the infrastructure is necessary to achieve the success of distance learning in the Jordanian schools, and this needs shared efforts between different departments. Additionally, allocating the necessary resources to prepare schools to transfer for distance learning is an urgent thing that needs a lot of work and effort by the ministry of education, ministry of planning, and ministry of finance as they are the responsible for providing the requirements of infrastructure to transfer to distance learning, as this type of learning showed its importance in light of COVID-19 pandemic".

The need for training programs ranked second, as training teachers to be able to effectively employ their technological competencies is one of the most important means for the success of distance learning, and this requires redesign the training programs provided to teachers before and during service. Furthermore, faculties of education in the Jordanian Universities needs to include a syllabus for computer skills using education technology as they represent the future of the education process in the different countries of the world. In her study, Al-Adwan (2019) recommended to work on promoting computer competencies among teachers as it represents one of the most important reasons for the success of distance learning. Emphasizing this, one of the principals stated that:

"Working on promoting teachers' technological competencies is a necessary thing for the success of distance learning process, and it is a strategic option especially in light of the increased vulnerability to compelling circumstances as COVID-19 pandemic, which dictated the Jordanian schools to deliver the educational content via distance learning"

Furthermore, transforming the educational content electronically is a necessary thing for schools to provide the learning content for students and to make the teachers able to employ the learning activities included in the educational curriculum. This ensures confirms the need for school principals to provide effective

recommendations for curricula developers in the ministry of education as they are the link between the teachers and the educational authorities in Jordan. In this regard, one of the principals mentioned:

"Educational curriculum is the most important means of communication between teachers and students in distance learning process. The high quality, flexibility and employability of curricula in distance learning process represent the backbone of increasing interaction between teachers and students for the success of the distance learning process. This requires that principals make recommendations to educational departments in the ministry of education to benefit from distance learning experience in light of COVID-19 pandemic in order to convert to distance learning in the future".

Recommendations

In light of the results, the study recommends to:

- Working on establishing the necessary conditions to develop the role of school administration in the success of distance learning process under Corona pandemic.
- Providing the necessary means to provide an appropriate infrastructure, develop curriculum, and to provide training courses capable of enhancing school teachers' technological skills.
- Conducting future studies addressing the school administration role in the success of distance learning from other research samples perspectives.

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